

CONSTRAINTS FACED BY THE FARMERS IN ADOPTION OF GOOD AGRICULTURE PRACTICES

P.B. Chaudhary¹, S.P. Pandya², H.A. Chaudhari³

1*Ph.D. scholar, Department of Extension Education, C.P.C.A., SDAU, Sardarkrushinagar 2* Planning officer, Directorate of Research, SDAU, Sardarkrushinagar

3*Ph.D. scholar, Department of Extension Education, C.P.C.A., SDA, Sardarkrushinagar

pandyasp@gmail.com,

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Abstract

Agriculture is the mainstay of Indian economy. India's basic strength lies in agriculture, but its vast potential has not been fully exploited. While World Trade Organization (WTO) poses some challenges, it also offers tremendous worldwide market opportunities for Indian agriculture produce. This market potential can be realized by reforming agriculture and making its produce internationally competitive in quality and food safety. GAPs as defined by FAO, are a "collection of principles to apply for on-farm production and postproduction processes, resulting in safe and healthy food and non-food agricultural products, while taking into account economic, social and environmental sustainability". A study was conducted in Banaskantha and Sabarkantha districts. This both districts was selected randomly from six districts of the North Gujarat. Four talukas was randomly selected from each district. Three villages from each taluka was selected randomly. Thus, total 240 respondents have been selected for the study and was interviewed with a structural pre-tested interview schedule. Ex-post facto research design was followed for carrying out the study. The major constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of good agriculture practices was; High initial cost 92.50 per cent, Farmers getting less price of product as compare to MSP 90.41 per cent and Risk in adoption of new technology as compare to traditional 88.75 per cent. Major suggestion to overcome the constraints faced by them in adoption of good agriculture practices was; Timely supply of require inputs to farmers through government agencies at affordable price 94.58 per cent, Timely demonstration should be conducted so there is no risk in adoption of new technology 87.91 per cent and Provision of remunerative price for of farm produce 81.66 per cent.

Keywords: Constrains, suggestion, good agriculture practices(GAP)

Introduction

The concept of Good Agriculture Practices (GAPs) has evolved in recent years in the context of a rapidly changing and globalizing food economy and as a result of the concerns and commitments of a wide range of stakeholders about food production and security, food safety and quality and the environmental sustainability of agriculture. GAPs applies recommendations and available knowledge to addressing environmental, economic and social sustainability for on-farm production and post-production processes resulting in safe and healthy food and non-food agricultural products. A broadly accepted approach using GAPs principles, generic indicators and practices was help guide debate on national policies and actions and on the preparation of strategies to ensure that all stakeholders participate in and benefit from the application of GAPs in the food chain. GAPs as defined by FAO, are a "collection of principles to apply for on-farm production and postproduction processes, resulting in safe and healthy food and non-food agricultural products, while taking into account economic, social and environmental sustainability". The Four pillars of Good Agriculture Practices are the core principles used for the effective promotion and adoption of GAPs. By following these pillars, farmers can build their reputations as providers of affordable yet high-quality goods and keep up with competitive export markets. As described by FAO the four GAPs pillars are economic viability, environmental stability, social acceptability and food safety and quality. GAPs aim to bring balance into the food production equation. It helps all stakeholders of the food production chain to understand the importance of food safety, the necessity of a sustainable food production system, and the fact that we must not produce waste. GAPs do not prescribe techniques to increase crop productivity. It does however, help farmers to effectively produce

profitable and sustainable crops, creating benefits that directly affect them. The implementation of GAPs should contribute to Sustainable Agriculture and Rural Development (SARD).

Objectives

- To identify the constraints faced by farmers in adoption of good agriculture practices
- To seek the suggestions from the farmers for better adoption of good agriculture practices

Methodology

The present study was undertaken in North Gujarat. The study was confined to ex post facto research design as the independent variables have already operated in the study area (Kerlinger 1976). A multistage random sampling technique was used for present study. Banaskantha and Sabarkantha districts was randomly selected. Four talukas was randomly selected from each district. Three villages from each taluka was selected randomly. From each village 10 farmers who involved/ engaged in agriculture and allied activities was selected randomly. Thus, total 240 sample size. The data was collected by personal contact method with the help of structured pre-tested interview schedule and collected data was coded, classified, tabulated and analyzed in light of objectives and in order to make the findings meaningful for drawing meaningful interpretation.

Result And Discussion

The farmers might be facing certain problems in adoption of good agriculture practices. Due to such constraints, they cannot achieve desired goal. The constraints in adoption of new technology never end. Hence, it was felt imperative to identify the constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of good agriculture practices.

Table 1: Distribution of the farmers according to their constraints of GAPs

(n=240)

Sr. No.	Constraints	Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1.	Unavailability of seeds of latest high yielding varieties (HYV)	168	70.00	VII
2.	Procedure of seed treatment is very laborious	165	68.75	IX
3.	Shortage of labor	203	84.58	IV
4.	Improved/ latest farm equipments are expensive	146	60.83	XI
5.	Farmers getting less price of product as compare to MSP	217	90.41	II
6.	Inadequate information	189	78.75	VI

7.	Lack of appropriate technologies	167	69.58	VIII
8.	Uneven & erratic rainfall	201	83.75	V
9.	High cost of improved farm machinery	163	67.91	X
10.	High initial cost	222	92.50	I
11.	Location specific scientific technology cannot perform in every location	128	53.33	XII
12.	Risk in adoption of new technology as compare to traditional	213	88.75	III

It can be seen from Table 1 that the major constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of good agriculture practices was; high initial cost (92.50), farmers getting less price of product as compare to MSP (90.41 %), risk in adoption of new technology as compare to traditional (88.75 %), shortage of labour (84.58 %), uneven & erratic rainfall (83.75 %), inadequate information (78.75 %), unavailability of seeds of latest high yielding varieties (HYV) (70.00 %), lack of appropriate technologies (69.58 %), procedure of seed treatment is

very laborious (68.75 %), high cost of improved farm machinery (67.91 %), improved/ latest farm equipments are expensive (60.83 %) and location specific scientific technology cannot perform in every location (53.33 %) which was ranked as I to XII respectively. It can be clearly shown that High initial cost, Farmers getting less price of product as compare to MSP and Risk in adoption of new technology as compare to traditional was the main constraints.

Table 2: Suggestions from the farmers to overcome the existing constraints faced by them

A major suggestions of beneficiaries to overcome various problems faced by farmers in adoption of good agriculture practices.. The possible suggestion to overcome the constraints faced by them in adoption of good agriculture practices. (n=240)

Sr. No.	Suggestions	Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1.	Made available certified seed from government authorized agencies at right time & reasonable rate	182	75.83	IV
2.	Provision of remunerative price for of farm produce	196	81.66	III
3.	Timely supply of require inputs to farmers through government agencies at affordable price	227	94.58	I
4.	Easily and timely availability of adequate credit facilities at village level at nominal rate of interest	153	63.75	VII
5.	Scientific advice should be made available in timely at block level through subject matter specialist	178	74.16	VI
6.	Implementation training (IWM, INM, IDPM, Handling of farm equipments) should be imparted in time	180	75.00	V
7.	Timely demonstration should be conducted so there is no risk in adoption of new technology	211	87.91	II

From Table 2 is apparent that the farmers had suggested that the timely supply of require inputs to farmers through government agencies at affordable price (94.58 %), timely demonstration should be conducted so there is no risk in adoption of new technology (87.91 %), provision of remunerative price for farm produce (81.66 %), made available certified seed from government authorized agencies at right time & reasonable rate (75.83 %), implementation training (IWM, INM, IDPM, Handling of farm equipments) should be imparted in time (75.00 %), scientific advice should be made available in timely at block level through subject matter specialist (74.16 %) and easily and timely availability of adequate credit facilities at village level at nominal rate of interest (63.75 %) which was ranked as I, to VII. From the above results, major suggestions given by the farmers was; timely supply of require inputs to farmers through government agencies at affordable price, timely demonstration should be conducted so there is no risk in adoption of new technology and provision of remunerative price for of farm produce.

Conclusion

The major constraints faced by the farmers in adoption of good agriculture practices was; High initial cost, Farmers getting less price of product as compare to MSP and Risk in adoption of new technology as compare to traditional. Furthermore, major suggestions given by the farmers to overcome the constraints faced by them in adoption of good agriculture practices was; timely supply of require inputs to farmers through government agencies at affordable

price, timely demonstration should be conducted so there is no risk in adoption of new technology and provision of remunerative price for of farm produce.

References

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